

CONSUMER ATTITUDE TOWARDS BEHAVIOURAL INTENTION OF ORGANIC FOOD

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Abstract: The popularity of organic food products has been on the rise due to increasing concerns about the environmental and health impacts of synthetic foods. This article explores consumer attitudes towards purchasing organic food and the factors influencing their intention to buy such products. A quantitative survey was conducted with 245 consumers in Bangalore, India, using non-probability judgmental sampling. The analysis of the data reveals that health issues, environmental concern, and behavioral intention are highly rated variables. Correlation analysis shows that positive correlations exist between the constructs of health issues, environmental concern, trust, social reason, economic reason, and attitude and intention to purchase organic food. The study highlights the demographic attributes of organic food consumers, such as gender, education level, occupation, salary, and marital status. Furthermore, the measurement model analysis confirms the reliability and validity of the survey instrument. Overall, this research contributes to understanding consumer behavior towards organic food and provides insights for marketers and policymakers to promote and sell organic food products effectively in the Indian market.

Keywords: *Green marketing, green products, organic food items, behavioural Intentions.*

Introduction

Due to the expanding availability of synthetic food worldwide, organic food is becoming increasingly popular. Producing food organically means doing so without the use of synthetic chemicals or genetically modified ingredients. Consumers are worried about the effects of processed meals on the environment, in addition to eating more healthfully. With 23 lakh hectares under organic farming, India ranks first in Asia and fifth overall, according to the FiBL and IFOAM Organics International Report 2021. The survey also forecasts that India's organic industry will expand more quickly because of the increased demand for organic goods during the outbreak. Due to factors including nutritional value, flavor, accessibility, affordability, freshness, attractiveness, pricing, and other factors, consumers favor organic foods. Organic food has a high market price due to the low output, which is also the main reason why it is not particularly well-liked by the general public. Trust and mistrust become essential considerations when choosing where to purchase organic food goods and whether to do so. Food distance, price, and the certification process may substantially impact customers' decisions to buy organic food. The knowledge gap between the existing marketing system, the supply chain, and the value delivery network in the organic food system is the final difficulty the industry is now facing.

One of the main reasons people choose organic food is to avoid the harmful effects of chemical pesticides, herbicides, and fertilizers used in conventional farming. These chemicals can leave residues on the food and may adversely affect human health when consumed over time. On the other hand, organic farming methods rely on natural and sustainable practices such as crop rotation, composting, and biological pest control to maintain soil fertility and control pests. Another concern is using genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in conventional food production. Organic food products are not allowed to contain genetically modified materials. This is important to consumers who prefer to avoid GMOs due to concerns about their long-term effects on health and the environment. In livestock breeding, organic methods prohibit the use of growth hormones, antibiotics, and other synthetic chemicals to enhance growth or prevent diseases. Organic livestock is raised in more natural and humane conditions, with access to outdoor areas and a diet that is free from genetically modified feed and chemical additives. The increasing awareness about the benefits of organic food has led to significant growth in its production and consumption in recent years. People are willing to pay a premium for organic products because they believe they are healthier, more environmentally friendly, and support sustainable agriculture practices. This trend has prompted organic farming expansion and organic food availability in various retail outlets, including dedicated organic stores, farmers' markets, and even mainstream supermarkets.

Review of Literature

Anoy Basumatary (2022), According to this survey, urban areas account for the majority of consumers of organic food items, yet supply is relatively low and marketing tactics are subpar due to a lack of organic producers, proper market facilities, consumer ignorance, and outlets. **Anubhav Beniwal and Chidanand Patil (2022)**, Based on this analysis, there is a vast disparity between supply and demand, which presents a chance for other farmers, allowing new producers to fill the gap and reap the rewards. It advises farmers to engage in the organic food

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market to generate money. **Gagandeep Kaur and Monika Rana (2022)**, In accordance with this study, consumer purchase behaviour for instant food products is positively impacted by health awareness, knowledge of organic foods, subjective norms, perceived price, and availability; however, the relationship also mediates attitude and intent to buy. **Preeti M et al. (2021)**, This study aids producers of organic food items in developing marketing plans that emphasise aspects affecting consumer attitudes more than price, such as product quality, health advantages, and environmental friendliness. **Sona Srivastava (2021)** this study shows that customer attitudes and intentions to buy organic food items were significantly influenced by concerns about health, product quality, and education but not by environmental concerns. This aids in comprehending India's rising market need for food products made from organically farmed ingredients. **Karthik R and Senthilkumar K (2021)** rural consumers in this study were concerned about ecological imbalance and sought to change their eating habits to include more organic foods. This report recommends that the government lower product costs, improve manufacturing, and establish marketing channels for organic food items to increase the barriers to food product purchases. **Neeraj Dangi et al. (2020)**, This study suggests that eco-labels boost customer confidence in organic food by reducing information asymmetry and that personal considerations, including health and environmental concerns, education and awareness, price, and trust, are the most crucial ones when deciding whether to buy organic food. **Mohanraj M and Jaganathan A T (2020)**, This author demonstrates a factor that influences how customers perceive the knowledge, advantages, cost, and marketability of marketing materials for organic food items. Ultimately, this aids the vendor in compensating for the buyers' high liking for the goods. **Uma R and Selvam V (2020)**, Analysis of this research proves a moderate level of change in the shift from buying conventional to organic food goods. The purchase of organic food products is facilitated more by females in particular, and customers are also more prepared for an eco-friendly lifestyle in the future.

Sadia et al. (2020), this study critically assessed Mysore's organic food product marketing challenges. It was discovered that the promotion of organic food items is significantly influenced by certification, dependability, health and environmental concerns, as well as the flavours and quality of the products. **M Neelavathy (2019)**, states that organic food products have larger urban markets, so both farmers and the government must increase their output, and marketers must be creative and dynamic to keep up with shifting consumer preferences. **Dhanalakshmi A and Suryakumar M (2018)**, Through the use of a marketing strategy, the project aims to increase college students' knowledge of organic food items in the Salem district. Based on their incomes, the students depend on organic food products. Additionally, it implies that terrace farming makes organic food products easily accessible. **B Krishna Kumar and S Niranjana (2017)** As the findings of this study, demographic status separates consumers of organic and non-organic food items. Psychological aspects such as attitude, perception, belief, and intention have also shown favourable outcomes for the Tirupur district's organic food customers. **Majmudar et al. (2017)**, meet customer demand, this article recommends continuously enhancing the organic food distribution chain from producers to consumers and supplying stores. By holding programmes on organic foods, the government must ensure that the label on organic food bears the certification mark and increase the understanding of producers, sellers, and more people. **Jyoti Rana and Justin Paul (2017)**, that the rise in lifestyle diseases has significantly impacted modern customers' preference for organic food products. As a result, conventionally cultivated food is now given more weight in the eyes of health-conscious consumers. This demand for organic food items impacts businesses' retail, distribution, and marketing operations.

Conceptual Framework

According to Ajzen (1991), the intention to purchase a product is considered the best predictor of actual consumer behavior. Consumer attitudes towards the behavior significantly influence their intention to purchase a product. These attitudes are influenced by beliefs about the behavior and its consequences, which in turn affect the perceived attitude towards the product. Ultimately, attitude plays a decisive role in consumers' buying behavior. Recognizing the significance of attitude in consumer buying decisions, a conceptual framework has been developed. This framework suggests that consumer attitudes towards purchasing organic food products are strongly influenced by three variables: Environmental Concern, Health Concern and Lifestyle, Product Quality, and Subjective Norms. The proposed model for purchase intentions of organic food products is illustrated in Figure 1.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Recently, many consumers are turning to organic food items due to growing worries about the long-term health, economic, and environmental effects of genetically modified (GM) foods. Organic foods encourage the treatment of animals with greater compassion and provide hormone- and antibiotic-free meat. Farmers, merchants, marketing agencies, sellers, exporters, processors, and many other people involved in selling organic food items must use tactics and overcome problems from when the product is grown until it is consumed. As a result, this study attempts to comprehend how consumers behave towards organic food goods, as well as to examine the obstacles and sales methods for organic food products and offer solutions to the issues.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The increased health consciousness among the younger generation and millennials, high disposable income, rising popularity, and robust economic growth are the main drivers of the demand for organic food in India. Indian consumers are spending more on organic health and wellness items due to their more significant attention to their food's nutrient content and quality. This study aims to understand how consumers behave while buying organic food goods, assess the tactics and barriers to selling organic food products, and provide solutions to these barriers and coping mechanisms.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the motivating factors that impact the decision to purchase organic food
2. To assess the subjective norms held by consumers of organic food.
3. To assess the attitudes of organic food consumers towards safety and trust in organic food products.

Hypothesis

Objective 1: Motivating Factors

- H1: There is a significant positive relationship between [insert specific motivating factor, e.g., health concern] and the decision to purchase organic food.
- H0: There is no significant relationship between [insert specific motivating factor, e.g., health concern] and the decision to purchase organic food.

Objective 2: Subjective Norms

- H1: Consumers who perceive stronger social pressure to buy organic food will be more likely to purchase it themselves.

- H0: There is no significant relationship between perceived social pressure to buy organic food and the decision to purchase it.

Objective 3: Safety and Trust

- H1: Consumers who believe organic food is produced with safer methods will have a higher level of trust in organic food products.
- H0: There is no significant difference in trust level for organic food products between consumers who believe organic food is produced with safer methods and those who don't.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A quantitative survey was conducted with a randomly selected sample comprising 245 consumers of organic products from Bangalore City. Sample respondents for this study were chosen through a Non-probability sampling approach using judgemental sampling methods. Consumers who visited selected outlets during the survey time, and those who had time to fill in the survey instrument and were willing to participate, formed the sample respondents. The attitude towards purchasing organic food products was studied based on three variables: environmental concern, health concern and lifestyle consciousness, environmental factors and safety considerations. As a result of an extensive review of related literature, several items were identified that are believed to affect the consumer's attitude towards purchasing organic food products.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table No-1

	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	131	53.5
	Female	114	46.5
	Total	245	100.0
Education Level	SSLC	1	0.4
	HSC	14	5.7
	DIPLOMA	2	0.8
	UG	107	43.7
	PG	107	43.7
	Doctorate/ Professionals	14	5.7
	Total	245	100.0
Occupation	Student	2	0.8
	Private Employee	77	31.4
	Government Employee	3	1.2
	Business	6	2.4
	Homemaker	152	62.0
	Self-Employed Professional	5	2.0
	Total	245	100.0
Salary	Up to Rs 15000	12	4.9
	RS 15001-30000	48	19.6
	Rs 30001-45000	16	6.5
	Rs 45001-60000	14	5.7
	Above 60000	155	63.3
	Total	245	100.0
Marital Status	Single	1	0.4
	Married	192	78.4
	Separated	52	21.2
	Total	245	100.0

The above table reveals the demographical attributes of consumers who consume organic products. The above table shows that 53.5% of the respondents are male only, and 43.7% are well-educated at undergraduate and postgraduate levels. More than half (62%) of the homemakers prefer to buy organic food. For the consumers who buy organic food products salary level is more than 60000 in a month because organic items are costly, and 78.4% of the respondents are married people only.

The descriptive statistics, reliability statistics and correlation analysis of the data are presented in Table 2. The results show that health issues are a highly rated variable with a mean value of 4.50. Environmental concern (M=4.48), Behavioural intention (4.35), Satisfaction (4.28) and Attitude (M=4.31) are the other highly rated variables. The economic reason is the least rated variable (M=3.80). The reliability coefficient of the scale items is presented in Table 2. The level of correlation between the variables is calculated using Pearson's correlation coefficient and the value of the correlation coefficient level of significance is also presented in Table 2. It can be found that significant positive correlations exist between the constructs of Health issues and Environmental Concern, Trust, Social Reason, and Economic reason. Interestingly, the dependent variable attitude and intention to purchase correlate significantly positively with all the independent variables like Environment Concern, Health Concern & Lifestyle, Social Reason, and Economic reason.

Table No-2

Variables	Mean	Std.Dev	HI	EI	TR	SR	ER	ATT	BI	SAT
HI	4.50	0.722	(0.80)							
EI	4.48	0.755	.667**	(0.747)						
TR	4.10	0.839	.439**	.430**	(0.683)					
SR	4.13	0.791	.491**	.406**	.518**	(0.749)				
ER	3.80	1.145	.169**	.157*	.140*	.193**	(0.489)			
ATT	4.31	0.769	.685**	.638**	.531**	.531**	.175**	(0.853)		
BI	4.35	0.762	.468**	.381**	.427**	.533**	.256**	.547**	(.742)	
SAT	4.28	0.813	.544**	.509**	.417**	.579**	.127*	.642**	.629**	(0.801)

MEASUREMENT MODEL:

In this study, the researcher checked the composite reliability, convergent, discriminant validity check, SEM with AMOS, with moderating effect. In the first step, we conducted Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to reduce 31 items into a smaller number of factors based on factor loadings. All the items loading more than 0.915 were considered for the study (less and equal to 0.55). Kaiser-Meyer-Okin's value was 0.955, above the threshold value of 0.70. Bartlett's test of sphericity (Bartlett, 1954) was microscopic (0.000).

To test the measurement model, Cronbach's alpha coefficient of althea factors was measured between 0.70 and 0.91. The accepted value for the alpha coefficient is 0.70. The table below confirms the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) results.

Particulars	Calculated Value	Recommend value
C-Min	123.787	<3
Degrees of Freedom(d.f.)	102	
C-Min / d.f.	1.213	
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.967	>0.9
Normalized Fit Index (NFI)	0.959	>0.8
Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)	0.808	>0.9
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.023	<0.08

Conclusion

After conducting a thorough analysis of literature covering a span of three decades, our study identifies several promising areas for future research, including distribution, marketing, ethical consumerism, and more. These areas hold the potential to contribute to the growth of the organic food market and expand its global reach directly or indirectly. Notably, our research underscores the strong interest of consumers in developing countries to embrace organic food, a trend already well-established in developed nations. However, the limited effectiveness of distribution and promotion systems poses a significant challenge to the accessibility of organic food. Nevertheless, this challenge also presents an opportunity to enhance the availability of organic food and make it more readily accessible to consumers.

The public's overall awareness of organic food products is increasing, and their attitude towards purchasing them is positive. The study's findings also indicate that consumers have various reasons for buying organic food products, with their motivations primarily driven by environmental concerns, health concerns, social, trust the organic products, and economic reasons. Consumer behaviour encompasses the psychological processes involved in recognizing needs, seeking solutions, gathering, and interpreting information, making plans and implementing them, deciding on purchases, and exhibiting post-purchase behaviour. The consumers' attitude leads towards buying intentions and satisfaction with organic food items. That has been proven with the above model, and it clearly indicates that factors are stimulating the consumers' attitude and behavioural intentions and the buyers' satisfaction. It is crucial to understand the impact of society on the environment. In today's world, consumer behaviour is shifting towards purchasing environmentally friendly and organic products due to growing awareness of environmental degradation and related issues.

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